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ABSTRACTS

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N-acetyl glucosamine modified Boltorn H40 nanoconstructs for pH-sensitive delivery of anti-cancer drugs to cancer tissues

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Abstract

Breast cancer is the most common cancer in the world, accounting for more than 10% of all new cancer cases each year. Breast cancer treatment options currently available are scarce and ineffective. Targeted delivery of anti-cancer drugs specifically to cancer cells can be more effective than conventional chemotherapy. Dendrimers have played a crucial role in targeted delivery of chemotherapeutic agents. Dendritic structures can be easily functionalized for specific tasks like targeting and cargo delivery. Boltorn H40 is a polyester-structured dendritic polymer which is biodegradable in the tumor microenvironment causing rapid drug release. In this study, we developed a bis-MPA-based dendrimer H40-Boltorn-NAG (N-acetyl glucosamine) conjugate for increased drug loading and increased cellular uptake through GLUT transporters. The nanocarriers were characterized by ¹H NMR, dynamic light scattering, and FTIR. Confocal microscopy of DOX-loaded H40-NAG and H40 showed increased DOX accumulation in case of H40-NAG compared to the H40 only. Drug-loaded H40-NAG and H40 were evaluated on MDA-MB-231 and 4T1 cancer cells for measuring the cytotoxicity. DOX-loaded H40-NAG has shown pH-responsive release and higher cytotoxicity against breast cancer cells than the unmodified H40. The results suggested that GLUT transporters targeted hyperbranched bis-MPA polyester dendrimer carrying anti-cancer drug have excellent ability to effectively kill breast cancer cells.

Keywords: Cancer Nanomedicine, targeted drug delivery, EPR, GLUT transporters, bis-MPA polyester dendrimer.

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